

IMPACT OF FINANCIAL AND NON FINANCIAL BARRIERS IN DEVELOPING WOMEN ENTREPRENEURSHIP

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ABSTRACT

“Even in the twenty-first century, women entrepreneurs from all over the world continue to encounter different types of barriers in their activity. Depending on their location, history, culture, etc. the restraints can be more or less strict, distinct or similar.” This article analyses and compares the constraints either financial or non-financial that the women entrepreneurs from Rajasthan, India are encountering, barriers concerning the professional stereotype.

The study was descriptive-cum-exploratory in nature and convenient sampling technique was followed. The study is entirely based on data that was collected through secondary and primary case studies. The findings revealed that finance is the main barriers for developing women entrepreneurship in Rajasthan other non financial barriers includes “lack of family support, non-cooperation of male counterparts, weak bargaining position, psychological barriers, lack of experience, lack of knowledge, lack of society support, harassment, difficulties in getting loans to set up a business, lack of awareness about credit facilities for women, lack of infrastructure facilities, strict regulations and policies, attracting customers, lack of marketing skills and unfavorable market behaviors were the major problems faced by the women entrepreneurs.”

KEYWORDS- Banks, Women entrepreneurs, Barriers, Financial, Non – Financial

1. INTRODUCTION

WOMEN ENTREPRENEURSHIP

IFC define women owned business is the business in which 51percent stake held by a woman/women or 20 percent owned by a woman/women AND 1 woman as CEO/COO and more than or equal to 30 percent of board o directors should be women where board exist.

World Economic forum define women owned business-

- (a) 51% stake held by one or more women.
- (b) Long term plan and management and day to day activities held by one or more women
- (c) Contribution of capital or expertise by women
- (d) Operate independently business from other non certified business.

According to **Researcher** “Women who innovate, imitate or adopt economic activity are called ‘women entrepreneurs’.”

According to **Researcher** “The units in which women entrepreneurs have a majority shareholding and management control would be defined as ‘Women Enterprises’.”

“Women entrepreneurs are the woman or a group of women who initiate, organize and operate a business enterprise. The Government of India notes women entrepreneurs as, “an enterprise owned and controlled by women saving a minimum financial interest of 51 percent of the capital and giving at least 51 percent of the employment generated in the enterprise to women.”

With the emergence of women in the field of entrepreneurship, researchers have resorted to arrive at a comprehensive definition of women entrepreneur. Women who take onus to organize and manage the resources of their enterprises and bear all the risks in expectations of deriving profit can be termed as women entrepreneur. This definition portrays women entrepreneurs as conscious decision makers and managers (*Coughlin, J. H., & Thomas, A. R., 2002*). Women who chose to pursue the challenging role of an entrepreneur driven by their desire to fulfil their need of independence and achievement. This definition is only applicable to women entrepreneurs who are opportunity driven, i.e. women who resort to entrepreneurship driven by their free will. This definition excludes necessity driven entrepreneurs who are forced to pursue entrepreneurship out of some bare need (*Dhameja S. K. 2002*). When a women or group of women embark on initiating, organizing and managing their enterprise, they are termed as women entrepreneur (Suganthi, 2009). Creative activity of initiating and operating a business venture leading to economic empowerment and social betterment of women in the society can be termed as women entrepreneurship. This definition elaborates the positive, social and economic contribution of women entrepreneurship in the society (*Munshi, S et al, 2011*). Based on the synthesis of available literature, women entrepreneurs in Indian context can be defined as women having dominant financial control over their enterprise, who either choose or are driven out of some necessity to take up the challenging role of an entrepreneur and embark towards starting, organizing and managing resources at their disposal in expectation of earning profits. Women entrepreneurs take conscious decisions in order to manage their enterprise. Women entrepreneurship also leads to social and economic empowerment of women.

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2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

G.K. Dutta's study (2013) “Entrepreneurship Development among educated unemployed youth in industrially backward areas: A SISI's experience" explains that people in the region lack interest for industrial venture. SISI (Small Industries Service Institute) was established in this region with the intention of speeding up industrial development and promote entrepreneurship in the industrially backward regions. Various measures adopted by SISI's for promoting industrial development and entrepreneurship in the area helped to encourage and enlighten the people in starting his/her enterprise.

Lakmisha (2013), in her study "Motivating Entrepreneurship-A Study" has discussed about how individuals can be motivated to take up entrepreneurship. The study covered 7 talukas of Shimoga district and 2 talukas of Devanageri district of Karnataka state. The author suggested that a proper training could

tap the potential of the aspiring incumbents to become entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurship is influenced by several factors like achievement motivation, need for independence, availability of financial and non-financial incentives, training etc. apart from this socio-economic, psychological and the cultural factors also influence and act as a source of inspiration to become entrepreneur. On the basis of this survey the author recommended that there is need on the part of financial institutions and banks to attract the entrepreneurs with variegated/ innovative schemes of finance. Apart from this there is need to conduct more EDPs (Entrepreneurship Development Programme) and the course content of EDPs should also be strong so as to make individual capable of pursuing entrepreneurship. There is also a need to make changes in the education system i.e. introducing vocational education so as to create positive environment for entrepreneurship.

H.V. Sundaran (2014) in his study "Developing Entrepreneurship in Assam: A Few Thoughts", discusses that like other states Assam is also facing the problem of educated unemployment. The youths are not willing to take up self-employment venture. For this, the suggestions were: creating awareness about EDPs, identifying potential students having entrepreneurial skill and trait and giving practical training, financial assistance, and stipend to prospective entrepreneurs. Author also suggested some other measures for the existing entrepreneurs help for expansion and diversification of their projects and updating their knowledge etc. Though these measures are illustrative only but if implemented will help the youths to take up entrepreneurship.

According to the author, in India over a period of time women entrepreneurs have started representing as a group of women who have broken away from the beaten path and are exploring new avenues of economic participation. This further makes their task full of challenges, as they have had to encounter public prejudices and criticism. Opposition from family and social constraints has to be overcome before they can establish themselves independently as entrepreneurs. He further adds that the risk is greater for women entrepreneurs as compared to that of their male counterparts. There are many hurdles and limitations which women face. Despite this their participation is showing a steady increase.

Kalpna Shah (2014), in her study "Women and Technology: Some Social Constraints" attempts to examine some of the social aspects which inhibit women to participate in the field of science and technology. According to her participation of women in industry shows a general declining trend and stagnation.

"The household industries provided the biggest source of self employment to women; they were the greatest victims of the process of economic transformation. Not only it affected the finishing of their products but the traditional way of production also proved very slow. Thus, skill wise and time wise they had to face stiff competition from factor production".

She further discusses that the recent increase in unemployment has led to a realization of the need to promote self-employment in all areas. There is a need for the development of the technological skill among women as a crucial programme to be accepted and approved by all development experts. For this, same one needs to fulfill two underlying assumptions. Firstly to mobilize and train women for certain technological skills through which they can reduce thin dungaree and hazards in their routine. Secondly, women should get self employment, as it will add to women's honour and status.

Madhulika Kaushik, (2014), in her study "*Entrepreneurial Competencies and Gender wise Variation*" has talked about various concept of entrepreneurial competencies which work as a determinant of entrepreneurial competencies among individual. According to author's findings those women entrepreneurs who are successful are significantly different from those who are unsuccessful women entrepreneurs. As per author, gender may therefore not necessarily a determinant of competence levels.

Ela Bhatt, (2015) in her study "Women's Employment and Technology" discusses the problems that are emerging out of the present situation. She has put these problems in three categories. According to the author, the first problem faced by women is unequal and lack of access to education and training in scientific and technical skills in modern sector. The second problem faced by them is that they still continue to "manage" the subsistence economy with or without skills, with "traditional" techniques - new technology aids men's work. The third problem faced by them is the introduction of new techniques, which displaces women totally, or else they are forced to take up low skilled, low paid and low productivity jobs. Hence the significant feature that emerges from the above-mentioned categories of problems is the profile of inequality of women workers in relation to technical training, inputs and know-how. She has also discussed the use of primitive tools and various occupational hazards in various occupations, in contrast to their male counterparts due to no or limited access to technological inputs at all levels; the output of their productive labour tends to remain constant and at times it is declining.

Jayanti Banerjee (2015) in her study "Implications of Technology for Women in the rural sector" concentrates on the implications of technology for women in the rural sector therefore can be viewed from two angles i.e. (i) negative and (ii) potentially positive.

The study concentrates on displacement of women workers due to introduction of new technology in various occupations. As per the author, it is very much in the interest of distributive social justice and national development that technology should not harm women's interest. On the contrary, women's interest should be harnessed and adapted to women's role and responsibilities especially in the rural sector. She also discusses about the improvement in working conditions at economic and domestic spheres. She further talked about transfer of technology. According to the author, one needs to take into consideration two aspects:- (i) dissemination of information and (ii) extension. Further elaborating her discussion she talks about, the choice of technology. With regard to the implications of technology on rural women she had recommended options and methods for technology adoption, certain ideological factors that one needs to keep in mind.

A. S. Seetharamu(2016) in his study on "*Women in Organized Movement*" talks about the women who belong to various professional organizations. In this study the author has made an attempt to study the role of women in the professional institution and factors influencing their participation. The main focus of the study was to bring out the various constraints and problem faced by women in their profession. It was expected that the study would enable them to participate meaningfully in the professional organization. However, disappointing the participation of women was found in organized movements. This clearly indicates that there is lack of women to participate in organized movement.

Savitri Arputhamurthy (2016) in her study "*Women, Work and Discrimination*" has tried to find out the factors responsible for the existence of women entrepreneurship in Indian situation. According to the author, in the socio-economic development of any country, women play a crucial role. However, as a

result of discriminatory socio-economic practices, they are burdened with cumulative inequalities whether it is an industrially developed country or a less developed country. In the case of rural women, the situation is worse. It has been noticed that women generally take up those specific jobs, which their male counterparts otherwise usually avoid. This leads to a kind of job segregation in the labour force of a country. This further leads to many other consequences like wage differential employment and occupational discrimination. She is of the opinion that though the Indian Constitution has laid emphasis on gender equality, women are still being discriminated in various socio-economic spheres of life. There still persists gender inequality.

3. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- To analyse the concept of Women entrepreneurship.
- To examine role of financial barriers in developing women entrepreneurship
- To examine role of non-financial barriers in developing women entrepreneurship

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

“The researcher has used exploratory research method for conducting the research as it will help in finding a better result of the research and it will also help in the description of the state of affairs, as it exists at the present. The main characteristic of this method is that the researcher has no control over the variables; he/she can only report what has happened or what is happening. The data was collected from some of the secondary sources.”

5. FINDINGS OF STUDY

Various factors which directly influence women entrepreneurship are illustrated in figure 1.1 below and discussed briefly thereafter.

FIGURE 1.1 FACTORS INFLUENCING WOMEN ENTERPRENURSHIP

** Source: Based on researcher's understanding of secondary data*

1. PUSH FACTORS-

There are some factors which push women to become entrepreneur like Unemployment, Dissatisfaction with jobs, threats and harassment in jobs and mainly financial problems in family, insufficient family income, to find jobs etc so to improve economic conditions women develop existing business or start a new business. These factors may have more importance for women than for men.

2. PULL FACTORS

“Factors that work as entrepreneurial drive factors relate to independence, self-fulfilment, entrepreneurial drive and desire for wealth, power and social status, co-operation and support of family

members and a strong network of contacts. The most prominent factor is self achievement expressed in terms of challenge which helps women to start, run their own business and turn it into a profitable venture. When a strong need for achievement could not be fulfilled through a salaried position or when there was a desire to transform a perceived opportunity into a marketable idea, then these factors work for a person to start their own venture.”

BARRIERS FOR WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS

Women Entrepreneurs in India have to face many financial and non-financial problems. The banks did not trust the female entrepreneurs according to them they do not fit in with the pre-contractual perceptions of banks. Women Entrepreneurs in India have to face many problems to get ahead in the business world.

There are various barriers for women, which inhibit the nurturing of entrepreneurial talent among women, and place constraints on budding women entrepreneurs. They have to face multiple barriers for establishing their business set-up. Major barriers for women entrepreneur are socio cultural factor, access to finance and other correlated barriers. The discriminatory socio cultural factors, predetermined gender roles and gender-based expectations, confine women to traditional roles which in turn stop their creativity and restrict their autonomy and mobility. The attitude which is existing in Rajasthan towards the women is as homemaker and caretaker, and therefore constrained many married women from venturing into entrepreneurship.

Radovic-Marcovic (2006) identified that getting capital funded for women entrepreneurs is difficult because banks, supplier, does not show confidence in the women as managers and their business.

For current research purpose researcher has classified barriers for women entrepreneurship into two types (1) Financial Barriers (2) Non Financial Barriers. These are illustrated in table 1.1 below and briefly discussed thereafter.

TABLE 1.1 BARRIERS FOR WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS

FINANCIAL BARRIERS

- Lack of finance
- Legal formalities for bank loans
- Exploitation by middle men
- Availability of less financial products

- High collaterals
- High cost of production
- Low risk-bearing capacity

NON FINANCIAL BARRIERS

- Lack of education
- Lack of self confidence
- Lack of entrepreneurial aptitude
- Lack of meeting administrative and regulatory requirements
- Lack of management skills or training
- Lack of marketing skills
- Lack of technological knowledge
- Limited mobility
- Male dominated society
- Socio-cultural barriers
- Family ties
- Tough competitions

FINANCIAL BARRIERS FOR WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS

- **LACK OF FINANCE**

Women entrepreneurs suffer a lot in raising and meeting the financial needs of the business, Bankers, creditors and financial institutes are not coming forward to provide financial assistance to women borrowers on the ground of their less credit worthiness and more chances of business failure. They also face financial problem due to blockage of funds in raw materials, work-in-progress finished goods and non-receipt of payment from customers in time.

- **LEGAL FORMALITIES FOR BANK LOANS**

Fulfilling the legal formalities required for sanctioning of loans by banks and running an enterprise becomes an uphill task on the part of a women entrepreneur because of the prevalence of corrupt practices in government offices and procedural delays for various licenses, electricity, water and shed allotments. In such situations women entrepreneurs find it hard to concentrate on the smooth working of the enterprise.

- **EXPLOITATION BY MIDDLE MEN**

Since women cannot run around for marketing, distribution and money collection, they have to depend on middle men for the above activities. Middle men tend to exploit them in the guise of helping. They add their own profit margin which results in less sales and lesser profit.

- **AVAILABILITY OF LESS FINANCIAL PRODUCTS**

Though public and private sector banks had made few norms for providing specified business loan schemes for women entrepreneurs, but the availability and accessibility of these schemes are not upto the desired extent specially in case of rural women entrepreneurs.

- **HIGH COLLATERALS**

As mentioned in above point that public and private sector banks provided few specified business loan schemes for women entrepreneurs, but as mandatory requirement for loan security or collaterals are desired by banks, which act as a major hurdle in case of first generation women entrepreneurs. Collaterals and security norms are rigid by banks which limit the accessibility of specified schemes for women entrepreneurs.

- **HIGH COST OF PRODUCTION**

Several factors including inefficient management contribute to the high cost of production which stands as a stumbling block before women entrepreneurs. Women entrepreneurs face technology obsolescence due to non adoption or slow adoption to changing technology which is a major factor of high cost of production.

- **LOW RISK-BEARING CAPACITY**

Women in India are by nature weak, shy and mild. They cannot bear the amount risk which is essential for running an enterprise. Lack of education, training and financial support from outside also reduce their ability to bear the risk involved in an enterprise.

NON-FINANCIAL BARRIERS FOR WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS

- **LACK OF EDUCATION**

Women in India are lagging far behind in the field of education. Most of the women (around sixty per cent of total women) are illiterate. Those who are educated are provided either less or inadequate education than their male counterpart partly due to early marriage, partly due to son's higher education and partly due to poverty. Due to lack of proper education, women entrepreneurs remain in dark about the

development of new technology, new methods of production, marketing and other governmental support which will encourage them to flourish.

- **LACK OF SELF CONFIDENCE**

Women entrepreneurs because of their inherent nature, lack of self-confidence which is essentially a motivating factor in running an enterprise successfully. They have to strive hard to strike a balance between managing a family and managing an enterprise. Sometimes she has to sacrifice her entrepreneurial urge in order to strike a balance between the two.

- **LACK OF ENTREPRENEURIAL APTITUDE**

Lack of entrepreneurial aptitude is a matter of concern for women entrepreneurs. They have no entrepreneurial bent of mind. Even after attending various training programmes on entrepreneurship women entrepreneurs fail to tide over the risks and troubles that may come up in an organisational working.

- **LACK OF MEETING ADMINISTRATIVE AND REGULATORY REQUIREMENTS**

Problems with administrative and regulatory requirements were judged to be major issues of female entrepreneurs. Micro enterprises of all types can experience problems in meeting administrative and regulatory requirements, because of the disproportionate effect of compliance costs on small companies compared with large firms. As a consequence, it is not surprising that almost half the support organizations specializing in support for female entrepreneurs identified a problem for their clients in this respect. At the same time, with a few exceptions, administrative and regulatory barriers are more significant for female owned businesses than for male owned firms of a similar size.

- **LACK OF MANAGEMENT SKILLS OR TRAINING**

Women entrepreneurs lack management skills to a greater extent than male counterpart for businesses in general, perhaps because of their lower propensity to have had previous business experience. Although the contrasting fact is that women are better managers at home but difficulties in accessing business advice or support appears to be a minor rather than major problem for women entrepreneurs, a significant minority of specialist organizations felt that women are particularly disadvantaged in this respect.

- **LACK OF MARKETING SKILLS**

Marketing plays a major role in uplifting the business by taking the products to its users and regulates the cycle of production which ultimately increases the profitability of business. Lack of sales and marketing skills is the most commonly reported barrier faced by various female entrepreneurs, after finance. The fact that this is a characteristic shared with many other micro enterprises and small firms does not make it any less important to female entrepreneurs. It may be seen as part of a general need to raise the level of management skills and competencies in female owned and other small businesses.

- **LACK OF TECHNOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE**

The state being lagging behind in technological advancements additionally suffering from pangs of illiteracy and especially women education access to technology and problems with intellectual property protection are regarded as barriers for women entrepreneurs. The lack of computer knowledge of women entrepreneurs is a major problem as computer skills upholds an significant importance in every aspect of business enterprise.

- **LIMITED MOBILITY**

Women mobility in India is highly limited and has become a problem due to traditional values and inability to drive vehicles. Moving alone and asking for a room to stay out in the night for business

purposes are still looked upon with suspicious eyes. Sometimes, younger women feel uncomfortable in dealing with men who show extra interest in them than work related aspects.

- **MALE DOMINATED SOCIETY**

Even though our constitution speaks of equality between gender, male chauvinism is still the order of the day. Women are not treated equal to men. Their entry to business requires the approval of the head of the family. Entrepreneurship has traditionally been seen as a male preserve. All these put a break in the growth of women entrepreneurs.

- **SOCIO-CULTURAL BARRIERS**

The traditions and customs prevailed in Indian societies towards women sometimes stand as an obstacle before them to grow and prosper. Castes and religions dominate with one another and hinder women entrepreneurs too. In rural areas, they face more social barriers. They are always seen with suspicious eyes.

- **FAMILY TIES**

Women in India are very emotionally attached to their families. They are supposed to attend to all the domestic work, to look after the children and other members of the family. They are over burden with family responsibilities like extra attention to husband, children and in laws which take away a lots of their time and energy. In such situation, it will be very difficult to concentrate and run the enterprise successfully.

- **TOUGH COMPETITIONS**

Usually women entrepreneurs employ low technology in the process of production. In a market where the competition is too high, they have to fight hard to survive in the market against the organised sector and their male counterpart who have vast experience and capacity to adopt advanced technology in managing enterprises.

6. CONCLUSION

There are various barriers for women, which inhibit the nurturing of entrepreneurial talent among women, and place constraints on budding women entrepreneurs. They have to face multiple barriers for establishing their business set-up. Major barriers for women entrepreneur are socio cultural factor, access to finance and other correlated barriers. The discriminatory socio cultural factors, predetermined gender roles and gender-based expectations, confine women to traditional roles which in turn stop their creativity and restrict their autonomy and mobility. The attitude which is existing in Rajasthan towards the women is as homemaker and caretaker, and therefore constrained many married women from venturing into entrepreneurship. Depending on their location, history, culture, etc. the restraints can be more or less strict, distinct or similar. This article analyses and compares the constraints either financial or non-financial that the women entrepreneurs from Rajasthan , India are encountering, barriers concerning the professional stereotype.

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REFERENCES

- Ahooja Krishna (1979), “Women in Industry in Developing Countries”, *Mainstream*, Vol. 17, No. 28, March 10
- Alison Rieple and Shailendra Vyankamam, (1994), “Corporate Entrepreneurship: A Review”, in, “*The Journal of Entrepreneurship*”, Volume 3, Number 1, Sage Publications, New Delhi
- Das Malhka, (1999), “Women Entrepreneurs From Southern India: An Exploratory Study”, in, “*The Journal of Entrepreneurship*”, Volume 8, Number 2, Sage Publications, New Delhi
- Ganeshan V (2013), “Socio-Economic Basis of Women Entrepreneurship”, *SEDME*, Vol. 17, No.1, Pg 105-109
- Higgins Mark, (1994), “Racehorses or Rabbits? Are Entrepreneurs Scarce Resources? In “*The Journal of Entrepreneurship*”, Volume 8, Number 2, Sage Publications, New Delhi
- Kalpana Singh (2005), “ Women’s Work, Welfare and Status- Forces of Traditional and Change in India”, *Economic and Political Weekly*, Vol. 20, No. 51
- Mitra Ashok (1978), “Employment of Women”, *Manpower Journal*, Vol.14, No. 1
- Munshi S and Patel J, (2011), “Growth of Informal Sector in Rajasthan”, *The Business Review*, volume 6, Number 1&2, Pg 117-118
- N. Rajendran, (2003), “Problems and Prospects of Women Entrepreneurs”, *SEDME*, Vol. 30, No. 4
- Peter Drucker, (1995), “What Young Entrepreneurs Think and Do: A Study of Second Generation Business Entrepreneurs”, “*The Journal of Entrepreneurship*”, Volume 8, Number 1, Sage Publications, New Delhi
- Radovic K and Marcovic C C (2006) “The Problems of Women in Indian Industries”, *Social Welfare*, Vol. 4, No. 12
- Rayappa Hanumantha. P and Deepak Grover (1973), “Modernisation and Female Work Participation”, *Demography India*, Vol. 1, No.1
- Reynolds H (2004), “Employment of Women in India - Recent Trends”, *National Labour Institute Bulletin*, Vol. X, No 3
- Richard Caputo. K and Dolinsky Arthur, (1998), “Women’s Choice to Pursue Self- Employment: The Role of Financial and Human Capital of Household Members”, in “*Journal of Small Business Management*”, Volume 36, of Entrepreneur- Led Firms”, in, “*Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*”, Number 3
- Smith- Hunetr K (2013), “Women in Employment: Low in Profile, High in Discrimination”, *Yojana*, Vol. 19, No. 13 and 14
- Thakur Sanjay, (1998), “Entrepreneurs in Export Business: An Exploratory Study”, “*The Journal of Entrepreneurship*”, Volume 7, Number 1, Sage Publications, New Delhi